

Cube Subtraction in SAT Solvers

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Abstract

SAT and ATPG are closely related; we propose a new algorithm for organizing the search in SAT Solvers. Its essence is to view each negated clause as a cube in the n -dimensional Boolean search space, and realizing that each of these clause-cubes denotes a sub-region of the search space where no satisfying assignments can be found. Starting from the universal cube, which represents the whole space, we systematically subtract all clause-cubes until we end up with a satisfying cube or an empty cube if the SAT formula is unsatisfiable. The algorithm for cube subtraction is the D-Sharp algorithm, initially proposed for test generation for PLAs. This algorithm produces a set of disjoint cubes as a result of subtracting one cube from another. We implemented this strategy in the well-known zChaff SAT solver. Significant improvements in execution time and number of aborted instances have been observed for the new algorithm. The test suite includes several hundreds of instances from the well-known DIMACS, IBM-CNF Bounded Model Check, and Microprocessor's Formal Verification benchmarks.

1. Introduction

Propositional Satisfiability (SAT) is a well-known NP-complete problem with theoretical and practical significance, and with extensive applications in many fields of Computer Science and Engineering, including Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Electronic Design Automation (EDA). The SAT formulation can efficiently solve large hardware problems, including microprocessor verification [1], automated test generation [2], bounded [3] and un-bounded model checking [4]. It is noted that SAT and ATPG are closely related. The ATPG controllability problem directly maps to a SAT problem: compute the set of input assignments that sets a net to 0 or 1 in a gate netlist, or prove that no such assignment exists. Observability can be mapped to Boolean satisfiability as well by using the notion of Boolean Difference [5]. ATPG for single stuck-at faults can therefore be solved

by SAT-solver as was shown in [2][6]. Conversely, SAT problems can be solved by ATPG tools, if the Conjunctive Normal Form (CNF) SAT formula is interpreted as a two-level circuit description. As a result, practical SAT solvers have received considerable attention and numerous solver algorithms have been proposed and implemented.

Many of the SAT solvers, which participated in the last SAT contest [7], aim at finding a satisfying assignment by variable splitting. Search algorithms of that kind are mainly descendants of the Davis Putnam Loveland and Logemann algorithm (DPLL) [8].

Recent research has highlighted the importance of the analysis of clauses together with variables for decision heuristics, which are empirically successful on real-world industrial instances. The Variable State Independent Decaying Sum (VSIDS) of zChaff [9] scores variables for locality centric decision-making. In Berkmin [10], the authors claimed that VSIDS alone is not sufficiently dynamic, and proposed organizing the conflict clauses in a list, picking the next decision variable from the top-most unsatisfied clause in the list. Looking at the SAT contest results [7] we can see the advantages of clause-based decision heuristics. By analyzing the zChaff old version against the latest version [11] we can detect the precedence of this conflict learned clause list over the VSIDS decision heuristic. If no clause is found in the list then the decision process relies on the VSIDS heuristic.

Another work on clause-based analysis [12] maintains the clause list with both the conflict clause and the initial clauses, increasing the chances of picking inter-related variables. The next variable is picked from the top-most un-satisfied clause and no secondary heuristic is necessary. The implementation shows speedups over both zChaff and Berkmin.

Our approach goes deeper in this clause analysis. After a backtrack, we identify a problematic clause of the decision variable in question, and we continuously insist on variables from this clause. If more conflicts are found we remain in this clause until no more conflicts are caused or we backtrack past it. We call this technique the D-Sharp Strategy as the basics of it relies on the sharp (#) operator for cube subtraction.

One of the benefits of this approach is that it tries to identify a clause or a group of clauses that can lead to unsatisfiability, if the problem is UNSAT, or which are hard to satisfy if the problem is SAT.

This paper is organized as follows. The next section provides basic definitions. In section 3 we introduce the D-Sharp algorithm and how it is applied to SAT. In section 4 we show how the strategy has been implemented in the zChaff2004 version. In section 5 we report results comparing the original zChaff2004 with the D-Sharp version on industrial benchmarks from the DIMACS, IBM-CNF Bounded Model Check, Microprocessors Formal Verification and other industrial benchmarks used in SAT contests. This is followed by conclusion and future work.

2. Basic definitions

This section introduces the notational framework used in this paper. Propositional variables are denoted x_1, \dots, x_n and can be assigned truth values 0 (or F) or 1 (or T).

A literal l is either a variable x_i or its negation $\neg x_i$. A clause w is a disjunction of literals and a CNF formula ϕ is a conjunction of clauses. A clause is said to be satisfied if at least one of its literals assumes value 1, unsatisfied if all of its literals assume value 0, unit if all but one literal assumes value 0, and unresolved otherwise. Literals with no assigned truth-value are said to be free literals.

A formula is said to be satisfied if all its clauses are satisfied and is said unsatisfied if at least one clause is unsatisfied. A truth assignment for a formula is a set of assigned variables and their corresponding truth-values.

The goal of a complete SAT solver is to determine an assignment to the variables that turns the SAT formula true or to prove that no such assignment exists, in which case the formula is unsatisfiable.

A cube is a Boolean expression containing a conjunction of literals (logical AND). It may be defined as:

$c = (c_0 c_1 \dots c_{n-1})$, where $c_i = \{ 0, 1 \text{ or } X \}$, being X a *don't care*. A cube obtained from negating a clause is called here a clause-cube, what can be done by negating both sides of a clause getting a Disjunctive Normal Form. A cube c_i can be subtracted from a cube c_j and the result is a set of cubes that cover all the minterms in c_j but not in c_i .

Cube subtraction is normally denoted by the sharp operator (#). If the subtraction operation is defined so that the result is a set of disjoint cubes we denote the operator as Disjoint Sharp or *D-Sharp*. The algorithm we use for performing the D-Sharp operation has the same basic ideas of the one proposed in [13][14] for

faults in Programmable Logic Arrays (PLA's), and which is formalized next.

D-Sharp definition. Let $a = (a_{n-1} a_{n-2} \dots a_1 a_0)$ and $b = (b_{n-1} b_{n-2} \dots b_1 b_0)$. Then $a \# b$ is defined as follows: $a \# b = C$, where $C = \{ c^{n-1}, \dots, c^1, c^0 \}$ and each $c^i = (a_{n-1} \beta b_{n-1}) (a_{n-2} \beta b_{n-2}) \dots (a_i \gamma b_i) (a_{i-1}) \dots (a_1) (a_0)$. The operators β and γ are defined in Figure 1.

β	0	1	X
0	0	\emptyset	0
1	\emptyset	1	1
X	0	1	X

γ	0	1	X
0	\emptyset	0	\emptyset
1	1	\emptyset	\emptyset
X	1	0	\emptyset

Fig. 1: Definition of operators β and γ

Fig. 2: D-Sharp tree example

if any term of c^i is evaluated as \emptyset then c^i is evaluated as \emptyset (empty cube).

The algorithm can be best understood through an example:

Let $a = (10XX)$ and $b = (10X1)$

$C = (a \# b) = \{ c^3, c^2, c^1, c^0 \}$

$c^3 = (1 \gamma 1)0XX = \emptyset 0XX = \emptyset$

$c^2 = (1 \beta 1) (0 \gamma 0)XX = 1\emptyset XX = \emptyset$

$c^1 = (1 \beta 1) (0 \beta 0) (X \gamma X)X = 10\emptyset X = \emptyset$

$c^0 = (1 \beta 1) (0 \beta 0) (X \beta X) (X \gamma 1) = 10X0$

then $C = (a \# b) = \{ (10X0) \}$, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

3. The D-Sharp algorithm in a SAT solver

In order to understand how to construct a D-Sharp SAT solver, we start with a simple DPLL like description, without any further improvement such as non-chronological backtracking, clause learning, restarts or locality.

For a formula $\phi = w_1 \wedge w_2 \wedge \dots \wedge w_m$, we negate both sides and apply De Morgan's laws getting a Disjunctive Normal Form (DNF) formula $\neg \phi = c^1 \vee c^2 \vee \dots \vee c^m$. The disjunction of clause-cubes represents all the regions of the search space where no satisfying assignments can be found.

When we successively apply the sharp operation between the current search space and each clause-cube, we finish with the solution subspace of formula ϕ .

Starting with the universal cube u , which denotes the whole search space, ie.: $u = (u_1 u_2 \dots u_n)$ with each u_i literal having value X , the solution cube set S_ϕ is given by:

$$S_\phi = (((u \# c_1) \# c_2) \# \dots) \# c_m.$$

After each D-Sharp operation we are left with disjoint search subspaces. The remaining clauses must be subtracted from each of these subspaces. The choice of a disjoint subtraction operation avoids repeating the search in each subspace since they have null intersection by definition.

The algorithm of a basic D-Sharp based SAT solver

is explained next. The solver is defined recursively and is first called from the main routine with arguments $u=(XX...X)$ as the current search space, and $level = 0$. The pseudo code is given in Figure 3.

```

int Solve (current_space, level){
  if (level == last level)
    return (SAT);
  chosen_clause_cube = Decide ();
  C= Dsharp(current_solution, chosen_clause_cube)
  For each cube  $c_i$  in C {
    solver_return= Solve( $c_i$ , level+1);
    if (solver_return = SAT)
      return (SAT);
  }
  return(UNSAT);
}

```

Figure 3: D-Sharp based SAT solver pseudo code

The Decide() function is responsible for choosing the next clause-cube to be subtracted. The Dsharp() function executes the D-Sharp operation between the current search subspace and the clause-cube elected by Decide(). Like in a DPLL-based SAT solver, rules for reaching the final solution faster may be applied. A conflict is reached when a clause-cube covers the current search space. In this situation we backtrack. If a clause-cube has null intersection with the current search subspace there is no need to apply the D-Sharp operation, the result is the current search subspace itself. Finally, an implication (or Boolean Constraint Propagation) happens when the D-Sharp operation produces a single cube as the result. As can be seen, the set C in this pseudo code may suffer from memory blow-up, however it is left this way just for better understanding.

The D-Sharp based SAT solving algorithm can be better understood using a simple CNF formula example:

$$\phi = (\neg x_1 \vee x_2 \vee \neg x_4) \wedge (x_1 \vee \neg x_2 \vee x_3) \wedge (x_1 \vee \neg x_3 \vee \neg x_4)$$

Applying De Morgan laws to the formula we have:

$$\neg \phi = (x_1 \wedge \neg x_2 \wedge x_4) \vee (\neg x_1 \wedge x_2 \wedge \neg x_3) \vee (\neg x_1 \wedge x_3 \wedge x_4)$$

In vector cube notation we have:

$$\neg \phi = (10X1) \vee (010X) \vee (0X11)$$

Now starting with $u=(XXXX)$, which means any assignment for (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) , taking the first clause to subtract and applying the D-Sharp algorithm we get the result:

$(XXXX) \# (10X1) = (0XXX) \vee (11XX) \vee (10X0)$, which has three disjoint search subspaces. Note that the search sub-spaces have null intersection to avoid unnecessary search in overlapped regions, which justifies the use of the D-Sharp operator.

The complete search tree for the example is illustrated in Fig.4. Each level of the tree corresponds to the D-Sharp operation between the current search subspace and the clause-cubes, in the same order in which they are given. Note that, unlike the DPLL algorithm, the resulting search tree is not binary. However this tree can be superimposed in a DPLL binary tree, it allows us to benefit from all techniques that have been developed for SAT solvers: BCP, decision heuristics, non-chronological backtracking and clause learning, as explained in the next section.

Figure 4: Complete search tree of a basic D-Sharp based SAT solver

4. Integrating D-Sharp in a DPLL SAT Solver

We implemented a D-Sharp based SAT solver using the last version of the zChaff solver, downloaded from [15] as *zChaff-2004.11.15*. This version won the SAT 2004 contest [7] in the Industrial Category. We chose this implementation platform due to its recent improvements regarding locality, short conflict clauses and aggressive clause deletion. Comparing this version with a previous zChaff version, as mentioned, we detected the utilization of some Berkmin ideas on locality. This is accomplished by the insertion of a decision heuristic based on recently added conflict clauses executed before the usual VSIDS decision heuristic. Another important change is related with clause deletion. As evaluated in [11] 80% of zChaff's time was spent on BCP, thus motivating the improvement of clause deletion. This improvement takes into account the activity of the clause, which is increased every time the clause is involved in resolving a conflict, and the length of the clause.

To insert the D-Sharp algorithm into a DPLL-based solver, the D-Sharp operation defined in section 2 for a DNF formulation must be adapted to work into a CNF formulation. This is done by assigning the literals in a clause to obtain, in each tentative assignment, the

cubes c^i that appear in the D-Sharp definition when subtracting a cube that represents a clause yet to satisfy from the cube that corresponds to the current assignment of variables. We illustrate this with an example: Let ϕ be a single clause formula given by $\phi = (\neg x_1 \vee \neg x_2 \vee \neg x_3)$. ϕ is converted to DNF as showed in section 3.1 as $\neg\phi = (x_1 \wedge x_2 \wedge x_3) = (111)$. Starting with $u=(XXX)$ and performing the D-Sharp operation we get: $(XXX)\#(111) = (0XX) \vee (10X) \vee (110)$. The assignment $x_1=1$ is the same as the first disjoint search subspace (0XX), the assignment to $x_1=0$ and $x_2=1$ is the same as the second search subspace (10X), the assignment $x_1=0, x_2=0$ and $x_3=1$ is the same as the third search subspace (110). In a formula with more than one clause we may have conflicts after variable assignments. Only at this moment we associate the variable with a clause, and the next variable to be decided must come from this clause. To reproduce the tentative assignments as give by the D-Sharp algorithm, the next assignment is obtained by toggling the current decision variable and assigning a satisfying value to another variable from the same clause. In order to integrate the D-Sharp algorithm in a DPLL SAT solver we inserted changes in the clause database, in the conflict analysis, decision branching and in the clause deletion procedures, as outlined next:

a. Clause database

In the clause database, we create a new field for each clause, what we call *MARKED_CLAUSE*. This is useful to avoid the deletion of a clause associated to a variable when the solver runs clause deletion. In the same way we inserted on each variable's data structure a new field, which we called *ASSOCIATED_CLAUSE*. This is done to associate a variable to a clause, in order to keep the search restricted to that clause, assigning the next decision variables from free literals of that clause. We keep track of all the appearances of a variable in clauses, to be able to traverse all clauses of a given variable.

b. Conflict analysis and Variable decision

Recent solvers adopted different forms of conflict analysis but the first Unique Implication Point (UIP) has shown empirically higher speedups over other solutions [16][17][18][19]. An UIP is an assigned literal of the latest decision level dominating both literals of the conflicting variable. In this way, it is clear that the decision literal corresponding to the latest decision level is also a UIP. The UIP is normally UIP closer to the conflict side. zChaff2004 uses the UIP scheme for learning.

To identify a toggling decision variable we examine the variable's implication chain. If the UIP identified by the conflict analysis procedure has no antecedents then it is a decision variable. In this case the decision

variable is recorded and used on the variable decision branching and clause association.

If the UIP has antecedents then it is not a decision variable and our algorithm is not applied.

We let the original zChaff decision heuristics operate freely. When a new assignment is made, this means that all clauses satisfied by this assignment have been effectively subtracted from the current search subspace. However, shall a conflict occur we act upon the decision variable identified as responsible for the conflict, if there is one. Since this variable is now to be toggled, we check to see if it has been previously associated with a clause. If it has, then the next decision variable is another yet unassigned variable of the same clause, and the assigned value is one that satisfies the clause. If the decision variable has not yet been associated with any clause then we search all unsatisfied clauses in which this variable appears to select the next clause to be subtracted. Searching from the most recently added clauses to the original clauses, we select the most active clause and its unassigned literal with the best score as the next decision variable.

Notice that only here a deterministic procedure for choosing variables and values replaces the traditional heuristic procedures used to this aim: the next variable *must* be from the same clause associated with the current variable just toggled, and its value *must* satisfy the clause. The clause selection uses activity metrics, and an additional level of dynamicity is obtained by searching from the newly learned clauses towards the original clauses, including these.

c. Learned clause deletion

In clause deletion we do not allow deletion of any marked clauses, which causes a slight increase in the clause database. The fact that we apply our algorithm only when the search is backtracking keeps the number of marked clauses low. Furthermore we disregard back-tracks which result in toggling a Unique Implication Point (UIP). We consider these as necessary assignments and not as decisions. Since most backtracks end at UIPs, we guarantee that the number of marked clauses is indeed low.

5. Experimental results

All the experiments were done on a Pentium 4 machine at 2.0 GHz with 2Gbytes of memory on Linux.

The examples in Table 1 are part of the IBM-CNF Bounded Model Check benchmarks. These benchmarks come from different real-life hardware formal verification problems. The complete benchmark set can be downloaded from [20], and for a complete discussion on the IBM CNF benchmarks see [21]. These benchmarks were used in the SAT2004 and

SAT2005 competitions. Table 1 compare zChaff-2004 with our D-Sharp approach in terms of performance (CPU time) and robustness (number of aborted instances). The column inst. shows the number of instances used, the time-out was set to 5000 seconds. From these results it is clear that the D-Sharp algorithm performs better and is more robust, especially for industrial families. The results where the CPU time or number of aborted instances is lower for the D-Sharp approach are highlighted in bold font.

Table 1: Results on IBM-CNF, BMC series benchmarks, time-out=5000 sec. (models 2002 and 2004)

Class of benchmark (IBM-BMC) IBM-FV	inst	zChaff (2004)		Dsharp	
		Time (sec.)	Aborts	Time (sec.)	Aborts
2004_01	11	10204	0	5633	0
2004_07	11	209	0	93	0
2004_01_11	11	24512	3	23963	3
2004_2_14	11	10119	1	9504	0
2004_18	11	32730	6	30101	5
2004_20	11	29702	5	28349	5
2004_23	11	32238	6	30198	4
2002_01	17	20367	6	20346	5
2002_02_1_1	17	2064	0	1921	0
2002_02_1_2	17	1454	0	1336	0
2002_02_1_3	17	3163	1	3201	1
2002_02_1_4	17	132	0	72	0
2002_02_2	17	3.9	0	3.9	0
2002_02_3_1	17	731	0	274	0
2002_02_3_2	17	84	0	123	0
2002_02_3_3	17	420	0	337	0
2002_02_3_4	17	257	0	39.9	0
2002_02_3_5	17	235	0	227	0
2002_02_3_6	17	320	0	70	0
2002_02_3_7	17	630	0	639	0
2002_03_	17	18656	5	15508	2
2002_04_	17	16099	4	17039	4
2002_05_	17	11803	2	12072	2
2002_06_	17	19257	4	20223	4
2002_07_	17	1062	0	161	0
2002_09_	17	14.6	0	5.9	0

The same situation repeats on Table 2, which is generated from logic circuits problems. The SAT problems are derived from formal verification of superscalar and VLIW microprocessors, buggy variants of VLIW microprocessors, liveness of single-issue pipelined and dual-issue super-scalar DLX processor. Some of these benchmarks were used in the SAT competition. The complete series of benchmarks and descriptions can be downloaded from [22]. The time-out was set to 5000 seconds

In Table 3 a mix of benchmarks, DIMACS, Planning and SAT-encoded bounded model checking instances are shown. The complete series and descriptions can be downloaded from [23]. The time-out was set to 1000 seconds. Here the results of D-

Sharp are similar to those of zChaff2004. Nonetheless, it is clear that for the industrial family Bmc the D-Sharp solver has again proved superior. The time-out was set to 1000 seconds.

Table 2: Results on Formal Verification of Microprocessors, time-out=5000 sec..

Class of benchmarks	Instan-ces	zChaff (2004)		Dsharp	
		Time (sec.)	Aborts	Time (sec.)	Aborts
sss.1.0_cnf	48	8.9	0	4.4	0
sss.1.0a_cnf	9	4.5	0	4.0	0
sss-sat-1.0	100	121	0	112	0
vliw-sat-1.0	100	2033	0	1807	0
fvp-unsat_1.0	4	108.3	0	100.5	0
fvp-unsat2.0	22	1756	0	1780	0
Livenessat10	10	40724	6	32653	5

Table 3: Results on DIMACS, Planning and Sat-BMC, time-out=1000 sec.

Class of benchmark (DIMACS)	Inst.	zChaff (2004)		Dsharp	
		Time (sec.)	Aborts	Time (sec.)	Aborts
Aim	72	0.1	0	0.1	0
Blocksworld	7	2.14	0	3.38	0
Parity16	10	7.8	0	9.8	0
Pigeon-Hole	5	15.6	0	15.7	0
Hanoi	2	159	0	274	0
Bridge-fault	4	0.06	0	0.06	0
Ssa	4	0.16	0	0.16	0
Beijing	16	506	0	823	0
Bmc	13	135.5	0	106.2	0

Table 4a and 4b are related and show details and results on individual instances. On Table 4a note that even on classes where the average improvement is small, we can find instances where the speedup is more than 2x.

Table 4a: Details on individual instances.

Instance	Vars.	Clauses	zChaff (sec.)	DSharp (sec.)	
1 IBM-FV-2004-18-SAT-dat-k20	34845	143320	71.8	40.4	unsat
2 IBM-FV-2004-18-SAT-dat-k30	52705	217310	2913	1370	sat
3 9-vliw-bp-mc-bug15	20110	287971	34.4	23.5	sat
4 fvp-unsat-2.0-7pipe	23910	751118	612	523	unsat

Table 4b shows more results for the same instances: the number of decisions, the number of added conflict clauses resulting from learning, the number of deleted conflict clauses and two D-Sharp statistics denoted 2^{nd} visit and *more visits*. The number of decisions is generally lower for D-Sharp, which is consistent with the reduction in CPU time. As mentioned, the number of clauses that D-Sharp deletes is lower because we do not allow de deletion of clauses associated with variables, which is low compared with the number of added clauses. The 2^{nd} visit column shows how many

times the second backtrack in the same clause happens according to our algorithm. The column *more visits* shows the number of times more than 2 backtracks occur in the same clause. This reveals that solving (subtracting) this group of associated clauses is instrumental for getting out of areas of no solution, leading easily to a solution if it exists or to a conflict, or proving unsatisfiability if it does not exist.

Table 4b: Solver details on individual instances.

	Solver	decisions	added clauses	deleted clauses	2 nd visit	more visits
1	zChaff	101939	24335	3744	-	-
	DSharp	73724	16375	1628	8281	101
2	zChaff	2009655	172250	97395	-	-
	DSharp	1609690	126416	44413	81299	512
3	zChaff	295098	13876	3471	-	-
	DSharp	235836	10035	1959	3993	40
4	zChaff	2151805	81540	56180	-	-
	DSharp	1693212	71773	37260	33035	223

6. Conclusion and future works

This paper describes an algorithm for SAT solving using cube subtraction. The clauses are viewed as cubes and are subtracted from the n -dimensional Boolean space formed by the variables. The algorithm ends when it finds a satisfying cube or when it proves that the result is an empty set (unsatisfiable formula). The subtraction algorithm is the D-Sharp algorithm, which produces a set of disjoint cubes as the result of subtracting one cube from another. This approach has been implemented in zChaff2004, a state-of-the-art SAT solver and showed good results on Industrial Benchmarks. This seems to be related to the ability to identify a clause or a group of clauses responsible for unsatisfiability, if the problem is UNSAT, or for problem hardness if the problem is SAT.

For future work we intend to tune the clause and variable metrics to work better with the D-Sharp algorithm. We use the metrics already implemented in zChaff. For instance, the age of a clause calculated during UIP conflict analysis is used but recent research has shown benefits of other calculations [12]. Moreover we believe the clauses marked by our algorithm may offer insights into unsatisfiable cores and their smallest size [24]. Moreover a clause deletion policy for associated clauses can be developed, which will reduce memory usage and increase robustness.

References

[1] Miroslav N. Velev and Randal E. Bryant: Effective use of Boolean Satisfiability. In *Proc. of DAC*, June 2001.
 [2] P. Stephan, R. Brayton, and A. Sangiovanni-Vincentelli: Combinational Test Generation Using Satisfiability. In *IEEE Transaction on CAD*, 1996.

[3] A. Biere, A. Cimatti, E. Clarke and Y. Zhu: Symbolic Model Checking without BDDs. In *Proc. of TACAS*, 1999
 [4] Ken L. McMillan: Applying SAT Methods in Unbounded Symbolic Model Checking. In *Proceedings of CAV*, 2002.
 [5] [M. Abramovici, M. Breuer, and A. Friedman: Digital Systems Testing and Testable Design. *Computer Science Press, N.Y.*, 1990.
 [6] T. Larrabee: Efficient generation of test patterns using Boolean difference, in *Proc. Intl. Test Conference*, 1989.
 [7] SAT contest. <http://www.satcompetition.org/>
 [8] M. Davis, G. Logemann, and D. Loveland: A machine program for theorem proving. In *Communications of the ACM*, (5):394-397, 1962.
 [9] M. Moskewicz, C. Madigan, Y. Zhao, L. Zhang, and S. Malik: Chaff: Engineering an Efficient SAT Solver. In *Proc. of 38th DAC pp. 530-535*, 2001.
 [10] Y. Novikov E. Goldberg: Berkmin: a Fast and Robust Sat-Solver. In *n, Proc. of DATE*, 2002.
 [11] Zhaohui Fu, Yogesh Mahajan, Sharad Malik: New Features of the SAT'04 versions of zChaff. In *SAT contest*, 2004
 [12] Nachum Dershowitz, Ziyad Hanna, and Alexander Nadel, , A Clause-Based Heuristic for SAT Solvers. In *Proc. SAT'05*, June 2005
 [13] S.J. Hong and D.L. Ostapko: Fault Analysis and Test Generation for PLAs. In *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, vol C-28, n. 9, Sep. 1979
 [14] J. E. Smith: Detection of Faults in Programmable Logic Arrays. In *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, vol C-28, n.11, Nov. 1979
 [15] URL: <http://www.princeton.edu/~chaff/zChaff.html>
 [16] J. Silva, K. Sakallah. Grasp: A New Search Algorithm for Satisfiability. In *Proceedings of the ACM/IEEE International Conference on Computer-Aided Design*, pp. 220-227, November 1997
 [17] L. Zhang, C.F. Madigan, M.H. Moskewicz and S. Malik: Efficient conflict driven learning in a Boolean satisfiability solver. In *Proc. of International Conference on Computer Aided Design (ICCAD01)*, 2001.
 [18] A. Nadel, Backtrack Search Algorithms for Propositional Logic Satisfiability: Review and Innovations. *Master's Thesis, Tel-Aviv University*, 2002.
 [19] N. Eén, N. Sörensson. An Extensible SAT-solver. In *Proceedings of 6th International Conference on Theory and Applications of Satisfiability Testing (SAT03)*, 2003
 [20] http://www.haifa.il.ibm.com/projects/verification/RB_Homepage/bmcbenchmarks.html
 [21] Zarpas E., Benchmarking SAT Solvers for Bounded Model Checking. In *Proc. of 8th International Conf. on Theory and Applications of Satisfiability Testing*, 2005
 [22] <http://www.ece.cmu.edu/~mvelev/sat-benchmarks.html>
 [23] <http://www.intellektik.informatik.tu-darmstadt.de/SATLIB/benchm.html>
 [24] Inês Lynce and João P. Marques-Silva, On Computing Minimum Unsatisfiable Cores. In *Proceedings of 7th International Conference on Theory and Applications of Satisfiability Testing (SAT'04)*, May 2004.